

Research Engagement Framework

Creating a Better World Together

Research Engagement and Impact Office

Framework for Research Engagement in TU Dublin

Research Engagement and Impact Office, 2024

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1. Vision, definitions and scope

Technological University Dublin's vision is to 'Create a Better World, Together'.¹ Research engagement is essential to doing this.

TU Dublin defines research engagement as an active partnership between stakeholders and researchers in the creation of new knowledge and practices. Stakeholders are the people most affected by, and interested in, a particular research topic - 'those affected by the problem being researched and those in a position to do something about it.'²

Engaged research is designed collaboratively with stakeholders. Engaged research addresses societal challenges and the UN Sustainable Development Goals.³

The aim of this framework is to improve how we work with external stakeholders, to achieve their goals and ours. This framework is written particularly for staff and PhD students, whether working alone or in teams in research hubs and centres. It will be of interest to anyone interested in collaborating on research to create a better world.

2. Introduction to research engagement

There are many different ways to engage with stakeholders on research. You might want to bring different perspectives and knowledge to your research questions, design or outputs. Someone might approach you about collaborating on a piece of research. You might have finished your research and be looking for ideas for how it could be applied. You might want to develop 2-way dialogue processes about your research through educational activities, to share your learning and learn from others about how it could be relevant to them. These different approaches can interact and cross over. For example, you might run a public workshop about your research, where you might meet people who have ideas for how it could be developed, and agree to collaborate to apply for funding to do this. There is no right or wrong way to do research engagement, provided that it involves respectful collaboration, for the mutual benefit of the stakeholders and for society.

Effective research engagement benefits everyone involved in the research process, as well as the research outcomes, policy and society.⁴ Research engagement increases the impact of research, and makes it more relevant to society.⁵ Research engagement has been shown to increase researchers' productivity, and increase their chances of securing funding.⁶

3. Principles and values

¹ TU Dublin, "Realising Infinite Possibilities: Strategic Intent 2030", accessed November 13, 2024, 6, www.tudublin.ie/media/website/explore/about-the-university/equality-and-diversity/TU-Dublin-Strategic-Intent-2030.pdf.

² Gabrielle Bammer, "Stakeholder engagement primer: 4. Options for engagement", *Integration and Implementation Insights* (blog), November 4th, 2021, <https://i2insights.org/2021/11/04/options-for-engagement/>

³ "The 17 Goals", United Nations, accessed November 13, 2024, <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>

⁴ Vocal, Medical Research Council, "Looking forward: working with the Medical Research Council towards a public involvement strategy", UKRI, February 9, 2023, <https://www.ukri.org/publications/public-involvement-review/looking-forward-working-with-the-medical-research-council-towards-a-public-involvement-strategy/>

⁵ See TU Dublin's Research Impact Framework [here](#) for more information on planning, monitoring and communicating impact.

⁶ Markus Perkmann et al, "Academic engagement: A review of the literature 2011-2019", *Research Policy* 50, issue 1 (2021): <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2020.104114>.

TU Dublin's values are excellence, inclusion, impact and respect.⁷ These clearly relate to research engagement:

- **Excellence** means holding ourselves to high standards in what we do and how we do it. We work to produce high quality, ethical research in collaboration with our partners.
- **Inclusion** means bringing a variety of stakeholders into the research process, for mutual benefit. Ideally we collaborate as early as possible in the process, so the research question can be designed with stakeholders. Some people's voices are not heard as often as others in the research process, if at all. We work with care to engage with them, their ideas and insights.
- **Impact** means that we want our research to be useable and effective. We want it to create positive change in society, whether in better products, practices or policies. We work with our partners to make change happen.
- **Respect** means valuing the insights, experience, ideas, knowledge and questions that each person brings when engaging in research. We treat people with fairness and empathy, and listen to their views, particularly if we differ. We treat them as we would like to be treated.

Guiding principles for authentic research partnerships were developed by Community-Campus Partnerships for Health, as follows:

- The Partnership forms to serve a specific purpose and may take on new goals over time.
- The Partnership agrees upon mission, values, goals, measurable outcomes and processes for accountability.
- The relationship between partners in the Partnership is characterised by mutual trust, respect, genuineness, and commitment.
- The Partnership builds upon identified strengths and assets, but also works to address needs and increase capacity of all partners.
- The Partnership balances power among partners and enables resources among partners to be shared.
- Partners make clear and open communication an ongoing priority in the Partnership by striving to understand each other's needs and self-interests, and developing a common language.
- Principles and processes for the Partnership are established with the input and agreement of all partners, especially for decision-making and conflict resolution.
- There is feedback among all stakeholders in the Partnership, with the goal of continuously improving the Partnership and its outcomes.
- Partners share the benefits of the Partnership's accomplishments.
- Partnerships can dissolve, and when they do, need to plan a process for closure.
- Partnerships consider the nature of the environment within which they exist as a principle of their design, evaluation, and sustainability.

⁷ TU Dublin, "Our Values", accessed November 13, 2024, <https://www.tudublin.ie/media/website/explore/about-the-university/strategic-plan/creating-impact/documents/TU-Dublin-Values--Staff-Charter-Final-Oct-2023.pdf>

4. Policy context.

Many strategies and policies emphasise that research engagement is important, even essential. This can be at international, national or university levels.⁹ Research policymakers and funders expect people involved in research to collaborate with stakeholders, to make research more relevant and to improve its impact. For example, at EU level, the Horizon Europe Strategic Plan (2025-7)¹⁰ and the five key EU research Missions¹¹ call for engagement between researchers, industry, and diverse groups in society. The aim of this engagement is ‘benefiting all of society’.¹²

In Ireland, the government’s vision for research is set out in the 2024 Research and Innovation Act. It emphasises building society’s awareness and understanding of the value of research and innovation. It calls for ‘engagement of members of the public with those engaged in research and innovation activities’.¹³ It also calls for ‘research and innovation that informs the development of public policy’.¹⁴

Research engagement is a key function of Technological Universities (TUs), as set out in the Technological Universities Act (2018).¹⁵ TUs are required to collaborate on research ‘with business, enterprise, the professions, the community, local interests and related stakeholders in the region’.¹⁶ This collaboration should ensure that the ‘innovation activity and research undertaken by the technological university reflects the needs of those stakeholders’.¹⁷ TUs are expected to deliver ‘research relevant at regional, national and international levels’.¹⁸ Engaging with stakeholders at each of these levels can help to achieve this.

Research engagement is essential to delivering goals in TU Dublin’s Strategic Plan 2024-8,¹⁹ such as tackling global challenges, and growing active partnerships across academia, industry, local regions,

⁸ “Position Statement on Authentic Partnerships”, CCPH Board of Directors, Community-Campus Partnerships for Health, accessed November 13, 2024, <https://ccphealth.org/partnering/principles-of-partnering/>.

⁹ For example: [Science Foundation Ireland Strategy 2025](#); [Irish Research Council Strategic Plan 2020-24](#); [Impact 2030: Ireland’s Research and Innovation Strategy](#); [Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2025-27](#); [European Commission Directorate General Research and Innovation Strategic Plan 2020-2024](#).

¹⁰ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Horizon Europe strategic plan 2025-2027*, (Publications Office of the European Union, 2024), 22, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/092911>

¹¹ “EU Missions in Horizon Europe”, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, accessed November 27, 2024, https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe_en

¹² European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Iphigenia Pottaki et al., *Fostering knowledge valorisation through citizen engagement*, (Publications Office of the European Union, 2024), 4, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/007501>

¹³ [Research and Innovation Act \(2024\)](#), section 9(1)m.

¹⁴ [Research and Innovation Act \(2024\)](#), section 9(1)n.

¹⁵ [Technological Universities Act \(2018\)](#).

¹⁶ [Technological Universities Act \(2018\)](#), section 9(1)h.

¹⁷ [Technological Universities Act \(2018\)](#), section 9(1)h(ii).

¹⁸ [Technological Universities Act \(2018\)](#), section 9(1)f.

¹⁹ TU Dublin, “TU Dublin Strategic Plan 2024 – 2028”, accessed November 13, 2024, <https://www.tudublin.ie/media/website/explore/about-the-university/strategic-plan/documents/Strategic-Plan-2024-2028-FINAL.pdf>.

community and society. Research engagement also helps achieve the goals in TU Dublin's Strategic Intent 2030,²⁰ including:

- being known for the **creation of new knowledge** and the development of timely and practical solutions that address the SDGs
- being one of the most flexible universities in **meeting the needs of stakeholders**
- being committed to **open science and open innovation**: developing and sharing knowledge openly, and creating **synergies with partners to optimise impact**
- having a **vibrant connected network**, well established and known for **delivering real solutions for the real world**.

TU Dublin's Research and Innovation Strategy²¹ depends on research engagement to achieve many of its objectives, for example:

- **developing our capability to address societal challenges** through initiatives that build capability and experience
- contributing to impactful solutions to societal challenges through **effective engagement with internal and external partners and communities**, helping **shape public policy**
- building ambitious and productive international **networks of research and innovation collaborations** and partnerships
- **engaging deeply with partners** nationally to develop outputs and insights that are translated into practical solutions that resolve challenges faced by society.

5. Key Questions About Research Engagement.

This may be your first time doing research engagement, or you may be very experienced at it. Every time you start thinking about a piece of research engagement, it can be helpful to ask yourself some key questions:

What? As mentioned above, TU Dublin defines research engagement as an active partnership between stakeholders and researchers in the creation of new knowledge and practices. Stakeholders are the people most affected by, and interested in, a particular research topic - 'those affected by the problem being researched and those in a position to do something about it.'²² Research engagement is about working with stakeholders on research, for mutual benefit.

Who? Who are the key stakeholders in your research? Who will be affected by the research? Who might be interested in it? Who has power to change things for the better in this area? How can you find the most relevant person to work with in an organization? You can find tips and references in the framework [below](#).

Why? The benefits and strategic reasons for doing research engagement are outlined above. What are your own goals in engaging with others? Do you want to increase your knowledge and understand new perspectives, to make your research more relevant? Would you like to start building a group or network around a particular research topic, so you can develop research proposals together? Do you want to find ways to bring your research to a wider audience, to exchange

²⁰ TU Dublin, "[Realising Infinite Possibilities: Strategic Intent 2030](#)".

²¹ TU Dublin, "TU Dublin Research and Innovation Strategy 2023-28", October, 2023, <https://www.tudublin.ie/research-innovation/vice-president-office-for-r-and-i/research-and-innovation-strategy/>.

²² Bammer, "[Stakeholder engagement primer: 4. Options for engagement](#)".

knowledge and ideas about how it could be applied? Are you responding to a request from an external partner? Or is research engagement required as part of a funding application? It's important to be clear about your goals, and communicate them openly to those you'd like to engage with. It's also important to take into account the goals of your potential partners or stakeholders. You can find tips and resources on the different purposes of engagement in the framework [below](#).

When? This will depend on your goals and those of your potential partners. If you want to collaboratively develop research ideas, you will want to engage before you have firmed up your research question. If you want to find ways to apply research you have already done, you will be engaging at the end of that process – but this is likely to start a new process. Or you might want to engage regularly throughout the research process, to really make the most of the collaboration. It's also worth thinking about what timing will work for partners – for example if you want to collaborate on a horticultural research project, farmers may not be available in May.

Where? Again, this relates to your goals and those of your potential partners. If you're looking to build relationships and speak to new audiences, you may want to physically meet them where they are. Sometimes a more diverse group can prefer to meet online. Or you and your partners might prefer to be on campus, close to relevant equipment or people. Talk to your partners to see what will work best.

How? There are many ways to do research engagement. The TU Dublin values (inclusion, respect, excellence and impact), and your goals and those of your stakeholders, will help you find the best path. To start, you can pick up the phone, send an email, or meet someone for coffee. You can use a range of engagement methods such as workshops, focus groups, roundtables, [future scenario workshops](#), [hackathons](#), [citizen science](#), or [arts-based engagement](#). You can join an existing structure which supports engagement, such as a [Living Lab](#). You can collaboratively write documents such as research funding applications, research reports, articles, blogs or policy papers. There is no 'best' way to engage, as long as you work ethically. So what kind of engagement will help to achieve your goals and those of your stakeholders? You can build and sustain your collaboration by reflecting on and evaluating it. You will find more information on how to approach engagement in the framework [below](#).

How much? There are different levels of stakeholder engagement, as shown in figure 1 below.²³

- **Informing** involves one-way communication or dissemination. TU Dublin's definition of research engagement requires active partnership with stakeholders, so one-way communication should be combined with more engaged approaches.
- **Consultation** involves limited engagement with stakeholders, keeping them informed and taking their feedback into account. This might be the easiest level to start with, if you're new to this area.
- **Involvement** means that you work directly with stakeholders to understand their concerns and goals, and include these throughout the research. You can do this regardless of whether they approach you, or you approach them.
- **Collaboration** requires the highest level of engagement. You and your stakeholders become equal partners in designing and doing the research. This doesn't mean that you each do the same things. Instead each of you contributes in line with your strengths and with your goals for developing new competencies.

²³ Bammer, "[Stakeholder engagement primer: 4. Options for engagement](#)".

- **Supporting** means researchers inputting into research that the stakeholders themselves design and carry out. This may involve less actual engagement than collaboration.

		INCREASING STAKEHOLDER INFLUENCE ON THE RESEARCH				
		INFORM	CONSULT	INVOLVE	COLLABORATE	SUPPORT
STAKEHOLDER PARTICIPATION GOAL	Researchers provide stakeholders with balanced and objective information to assist them in understanding the research.	Researchers obtain stakeholder feedback on the research.	Researchers work directly with stakeholders to ensure that stakeholder concerns and aspirations are consistently understood and considered in the research.	Researchers develop equal partnerships with stakeholders for undertaking the research.	Researchers provide input as requested to stakeholder-led research.	
PROMISE MADE TO STAKEHOLDERS BY RESEARCHERS	We will keep you informed.	We will keep you informed, listen to and acknowledge your concerns and aspirations and provide feedback on how your input influenced the research.	We will work with you to ensure your concerns and aspirations are directly reflected in the research and we will provide feedback on how your input influenced the research.	We will include you as an equal partner in designing and conducting the research.	We will provide advice and assistance as requested to help you design and conduct your research.	

Fig. 1: '2S Stakeholder Engagement Options Framework' (Gabrielle Bammer, modified from the IAP2 (International Association for Public Participation) public participation spectrum)²⁴

6. Framework for Sustaining Research Engagement.

The framework focuses on key elements in research engagement. The diagram (see figure 2 below) is presented as a cycle, starting at the top. This cycle could also be drawn in other ways. You can enter the cycle at different starting points, depending on your circumstances, and take different pathways through it – see the example below.

As you add elements of the framework to your work, your research should become more relevant and impactful. Your relationships with your collaborative partners should also become stronger and longer-lasting.

(This framework captures our current thinking, and is a living document. We welcome your [feedback](#) to help us develop and improve it. We will formally review and update it at least once a year. The TU Dublin Research Engagement Advisory Committee and the Research and Innovation Academy will review it every year.)

²⁴ Bammer, "[Stakeholder engagement primer: 4. Options for engagement](#)".

Fig. 2. TU Dublin framework for sustaining research engagement.²⁵

²⁵ This framework draws on a number of sources, including Campus Engage’s [“Engaged Research Framework”](#) (2023); Common Cause Research’s [“Building Research Collaborations Between Universities and Black and Minority Ethnic Communities”](#) (2018); NORC’s [“Community-Engaged Research Framework”](#) (2023).

As mentioned above, there can be different pathways through this cycle. For example, someone new to research collaboration might start by taking research they've already done, and developing a public engagement activity based on this (for example a workshop at a festival). They could design the activity to make sure they hear what the stakeholders think about their research. They could ask them how they could see it being made more useful to them. At that event they might meet a stakeholder who was particularly interested in their research and how it could be applied. They might agree to meet to discuss their common interests. They would then make time to build that relationship, which may or may not lead to collaboration on a new research project. That pathway would look like this, starting in the bottom left:

Fig. 3 – Possible pathway through the framework for someone new to research engagement.²⁶

To give another example, a researcher might be approached by a community organisation looking for a small body of research evidence to bring to policymakers to advocate for change. The researcher would then build their relationship with the organisation. They would co-design the research project with them, and do the research independently of the organisation, to make sure it is impartial. They might then collaborate with the organisation to jointly meet the policymakers. They would then agree to wrap up or build on the relationship and project. Their pathway would start on the right of the cycle, as follows:

²⁶ This pathway was suggested by Sophie Duncan in the TU Dublin Engaged Research Network podcast “What is Engaged Research?” (forthcoming) [link to follow when published]

Fig. 4 – Possible pathway through the framework for someone working with a community organisation looking for a small body of evidence to bring to policymakers.

The next section describes each element of the framework in more detail. [Section 10](#) contains useful references to help you explore the framework elements in more detail.

7. Guidelines for each framework element

7a. Identifying stakeholders who might share your research interest

If you're wondering where to start, try listing or mapping all the possible stakeholders in your research:

- Who might be affected by your research? Who might it bring hope to?
- Who might be interested in it? Who would miss it if it stopped?
- Who might be in a position to make change happen, if the research shows this is needed?

Figure 3 shows the different sectors in society, and the different groups in each sector. You can use this as a starting point to help you map your specific stakeholders.

Fig. 5. Potential Stakeholders/Partners/Intermediaries. (National Co-ordinating Centre for Public Engagement, 2022)²⁷

In figures 4 and 5 you'll find examples of stakeholder map for different kinds of research projects.

Fig. 6. Examples of stakeholders in a collaborative arts-based research project exploring Travellers' experiences of education.

²⁷National Co-ordinating Centre for Public Engagement, "Introduction to High Quality Public Engagement", YouTube, video, Feb 27, 2022, <https://www.publicengagement.ac.uk/resources/tutorials/high-quality-engagement-101>.

Fig.7. Examples of stakeholders in a research project to determine the levels of environmental toxins in community vegetable gardens.

Can you think beyond the ‘usual suspects’ when mapping your stakeholders – are there people whose voices aren’t often heard in this research area, who might have unique perspectives or insights?

You can talk to people inside and outside the university for ideas. For example, are you involved in a TU Dublin Research Hub, Research Centre or Research Group? If so, talk to the Hub lead or Research Centre/Group manager. You can also contact the [TU Dublin Research Engagement Lead](#) for ideas, particularly regarding community or statutory stakeholders. If you’re looking for ideas regarding industry stakeholders, you can contact the [TU Dublin ARISE Business Developers](#).

You can find a national database of community partners interested in collaborating on funded research [here](#).

Once you have mapped your stakeholders, you might want to think about each stakeholder’s position in relation to the research topic. You can use a matrix to analyse different stakeholders’ levels of interest and of influence/power in relation to your research – see the example in figure 6.

	Low interest in the topic	High interest in the topic
High influence/power		
Low influence/power		

Fig. 8. Table to analyse stakeholders' level of interest and of influence/power.²⁸

Think about how you can engage with those with high interest but low influence, such as members of underserved communities. Collaborating with stakeholders in these groups can make your research more inclusive. It can also be a way to support these stakeholders to increase their level of power and influence.²⁹

Patients and carers can have high interest but low influence when it comes to medical research. In Ireland, research engagement with patients is called 'Public and Patient Involvement' or PPI. This is not about recruiting participants to give samples or data. PPI is about design research collaboratively with patients, carers and others with relevant lived experience. PPI also increases the impact of research, as research findings are more likely to be shared and used³⁰. There is a wide range of PPI-specific resources available online³¹, including a short [blogpost](#) on how to identify and find potential PPI collaborators³². See also [section 10](#) below for further reading.

Think about whether different stakeholder groups might have positive or negative attitudes to your research.³³ It's worth sounding out both sets of people, to understand the issue from different perspectives.

7b. Making contact with stakeholders

You may already have a connection to someone in a relevant organisation or group. If so, you can tell them about your research and ask whether they, or someone else, might be interested in working with you. Or you may know someone who has a connection to a relevant group. In that case you can ask them to introduce you. It can be hard to identify the best person to talk to in an organisation. The person who monitors the main contact phone number or email address will usually have a good overview of who does what in the organisation. If you don't have any connection to build on, contact TU Dublin's [Research Engagement Lead](#).

You can start the conversation by phone or email, or, if it's possible, with an invitation to a coffee. Introduce yourself and explain why you are interested in working with them on your research. Describe why you think they might be interested, and how they (or others like them) might benefit. Give them an idea of possible next steps – for example the next step might be a planning meeting, possibly with others who are also interested. Can you give them an indication of how much of their time might be required? Be clear, open, and respectful of your partners' time constraints and

²⁸ Based on Mendelow's Matrix. See Ismael Memon et al, "How to: Conduct a stakeholder analysis when designing an educational intervention", Cardiff University Centre for Medical Education, accessed November 13, 2024, http://www.cardiff.ac.uk/_data/assets/pdf_file/0004/2741431/How-To-Conduct-a-Stakeholder-Analysis-When-Designing-an-Educational-Intervention.pdf

²⁹ NHS England and NHS Improvement "Quality, Service Improvement and Redesign Tools: Stakeholder Analysis", accessed November 13, 2024, <https://aqua.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/qsir-stakeholder-analysis.pdf>.

³⁰ Health Service Executive Research and Development, *Knowledge Translation, Dissemination, and Impact: A Practical Guide for Researchers. Guide No 8: Patient and Public Involvement in HSE Research. Research and Development*, (Dublin: Health Service Executive, 2021), <https://hseresearch.ie/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Guide-no-8-Patient-and-Public-Involvement-in-HSE-Research.pdf>

³¹ See the [PPI Ignite Network resources page](#) for a wealth of tools and guidance.

³² Edel Murphy, "Finding PPI contributors – it's easier than you think!" Health Research Board (blog), June 29, 2022, <https://www.hrb.ie/blog/finding-ppi-contributors-its-easier-than-you-think/>

³³ Ruth Murray-Webster & Peter Simon, "Making Sense of Stakeholder Mapping", *PM World Today* Vol. VIII, Issue 11 (November 2006), <https://skat.ihmc.us/rid=1JGD4CJZ4-F9CF0Y-1KM6/SEMINAL%20stakeholder%20mapping%20in%203d.pdf>

experience. Be realistic if you are discussing a timeframe, and don't commit to anything you can't deliver on. Give them an easy 'out' if they don't have the time or interest to be involved. This is hopefully the first step in building a sustainable research relationship.

Use your first meeting as an opportunity to listen – to get to know the partner, their context, their interest in the research area, and what their goals are for collaboration. Asking for advice, input, or involvement, or even sharing progress, goals or struggles can all help to build your relationship³⁴. Try to identify common goals, which you can focus on when you design your research engagement together. Communication is crucial in building a relationship, so find out what medium they like to use (some people prefer communicating through What's App rather than emails, for example). Ask them how often they'd like to be in touch - they might like regular updates, or might prefer to communicate only when something significant needs to be discussed or planned.

7c. Building relationships for mutual benefit - with stakeholders/ partners/ interdisciplinary teams

Whether a partner has approached you, or you have approached them, you will want to build a relationship to underpin your collaboration. You may also want to work with colleagues in other disciplines to do more effective research engagement. It can be helpful to recruit more than the minimum number of people to your research team. In this way, if people's availability changes, or they have to drop out, you can still sustain the research collaboration. Relationships tend to build, grow and eventually fade in a cycle. You can find more on the process of wrapping up relationships and projects at the end of the cycle [here](#). It can be challenging to maintain your relationship if your or your partners' context changes. You or they may move into a new role or even a new organisation as time passes. Can you make sure there are at least two people involved from each group or organisation? This will help to sustain the collaboration through these kinds of changes.

A key principle in relationship-building is to treat others as you would like them to treat you. This applies whether you collaborate with stakeholders and/or colleagues in other disciplines. Respectful listening and open communication are key. Both help to build trust, understanding, shared goals, and empathy. They also relate to the TU Dublin values of inclusion and respect.

It's important to listen for, and ask about, differences in how words are used across disciplines and sectors. Try to avoid making assumptions. It's also important to build understanding of the culture of each organisation or group you partner with. Larger organisations (such as TU Dublin) often have microcultures in different departments. It's vital to grow your cultural awareness as you build relationships.

Trust is at the core of effective relationships. Being capable, honest and reliable makes it easier for people to trust you.³⁵ Trust is built in a series of loops³⁶ - you commit to something and deliver on it, or you respond in a supportive way when a partner makes a mistake or experiences challenges in meeting a deadline. This builds trust for the next series of collaborative actions. You also need to be honest about your own mistakes and challenges. You also build goodwill when you make sure that

³⁴ Gorick Ng, "How to Build Real Relationships at Work", *Harvard Business Review*, August 19 (2022), <https://hbr.org/2022/08/how-to-build-real-relationships-at-work>

³⁵ Onora O'Neill, "How to Trust Intelligently", *TED Blog*, September 25, 2013, <https://blog.ted.com/how-to-trust-intelligently/>.

³⁶ Chris Huxham and Siv Vangen, *Managing to Collaborate: The Theory and Practice of Collaborative Advantage* (1st ed.), (Routledge 2004), <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203010167>

everyone experiences even small benefits from the start of the collaboration. When you are working collaboratively, it's essential to compromise – no one partner can have exactly what they want, so you have to be flexible. You have to take small risks, and let go of your control over some parts of the work, which can make you feel vulnerable. This is essential because it demonstrates your trust in your partner. (You can minimise the risks involved, particularly at the early stages, by describing your collaboration as a 'pilot', to each other and to others.)³⁷ Some writers argue that trust is a 'core metric' that can be used to evaluate collaborative research relationships.³⁸

Power dynamics and imbalances can sometimes undermine trust. Power can affect people's ability to contribute, to challenge what they see, and to make change happen. As you build a relationship with collaborative partners, be conscious that power can be visible and invisible. Power can take different forms, including knowledge, status, control, responsibilities, influence and access to resources.³⁹ It can depend on the situation, or be attached to a person's role, or be inherent in an individual. Even people who work closely together can perceive their own and each other's power differently, and it can vary depending on the situation. It can be helpful to watch out for situations where people might contribute very little, or might take over the discussion. They may be feeling different levels of power. If this becomes a pattern, it can help to tease out sensitively and respectfully with an individual partner what kinds of power they feel they have, or feel they lack. Can you collaboratively come up with ways to address any imbalance across the group? It's important to ensure that power can be shared between partners on research engagement projects.

Some groups can be fundamentally less powerful than others. Young people and vulnerable adults (for example disabled people, or people experiencing poor mental health) can feel excluded from power, and from research. It's important to create a variety of ways for less powerful participants to share their experience and ideas.⁴⁰ Those who are socially excluded and under-served are rarely included in research. It can take extra time and effort to find and work with these groups,⁴¹ but it will be worth it if they are stakeholders in your research. You should prioritise caring for the wellbeing of partners from vulnerable groups throughout your collaboration.

Key components of building research relationships and trust:

- identifying shared interests and goals, whether personal or organizational, to build common ground
- respecting different kinds of expertise and knowledge
- collaborating on research design and co-producing knowledge

³⁷ Note that in some sectors, a 'pilot' is the name for the second stage of collaboration, after the first 'proof of concept' stage. It is essential to check whether partners understand words in the same way.

³⁸ Milton Mickey Eder et al, "A logic model for community engagement within the Clinical and Translational Science Awards consortium: can we measure what we model?" *Academic Medicine* 88, Vol. 10 (2013 Oct) 1430-6. doi: 10.1097/ACM.0b013e31829b54ae.

(Open access version at <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3784628/>)

³⁹ Centre for Social Justice and Community Action & National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement "Community-based participatory research: A guide to ethical principles and practice" (2nd edition, 2022), CSJCA & NCCPE, https://www.publicengagement.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2023-10/d2587_how_ethical_guidance_report_aw.pdf.

⁴⁰ See for example the Hub na nÓg [resource pages for academics and researchers](#), for support for working with children. The Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth [planning Checklist](#) is particularly helpful. See also the National Disability Authority's [guidance for collaborative research with disabled people](#).

⁴¹ See for example this [NSPCC blog](#) on reframing responsibility for accessing services. These principles can also be applied to engaging in research.

- discussing potential challenges to collaboration - including contexts, histories and stereotypes that create inequalities and power imbalances
 - developing sensitive and robust ethical procedures
 - distribute funding across partners in a fair manner
 - creating welcoming meeting spaces, both on and outside the university campus
- (Adapted from Bryan et al, 2018)⁴²

7d. Collaboratively designing research project(s), and clarifying ethics, roles and responsibilities.

You might decide to plan a collaborative research project in response to a common interest, or a request from a partner, or a funding call that you feel is suitable. Here are some questions that might be useful to discuss with your partner(s).

- *To help you develop a research question:* What challenges are you or your partners aware of, or facing, that you might like to address through research? Which of the UN Sustainable Development Goals⁴³ inspire you? What practice-based experience and learning would you like to reflect on and share?
- *To help you identify the most suitable collaborators:* What additional knowledge, perspectives, and skills might be needed to address this research question? Would it help to bring in other people who can complement your skillsets and knowledges? (See also [section 7a](#) above on identifying stakeholders). Make sure you have good diversity and balance if you are putting together a research team.
- *What could be challenging in this process, and how might you address this?* Examples might be:
 - o the time needed for collaboration (especially if partners have other significant commitments)
 - o resourcing issues (e.g. if people change roles during the project, or move organization; the time it might take to recruit someone if you secure funding)
 - o differences in timeframes, goals, language, or communication styles
 - o changes in context and external pressures
 - o preventing and managing conflict.

Are you happy to proceed with the collaboration despite these potential challenges?

You and your partners will want to identify common goals. You can use exercises such as Purposeful Partnership⁴⁴ cards with potential partners to discuss and prioritise your goals for your collaboration. (These cards focus on museum-university partnerships, but can be applied to any research engagement collaboration.) What are your longer-term goals, that you would like to achieve in the coming 2-5 years? What is a realistic objective, first step, or minimum output, that you can collaborate on to start with, and then build on? What key result(s) would you like to be able to report on? You can develop your research question and approach together, based on these shared goals.

⁴² David Bryan et al, *Common Cause Research: Building Research Collaborations Between Universities and Black and Minority Ethnic Communities*, (University of Bristol and the Arts and Humanities Research Council Connected Communities Programme 2018), http://www.commoncauseresearch.com/files/2018/09/CC_Enablers_Barriers_final_sp-2c2f4bh.pdf.

⁴³ “[The 17 Goals](#)”, United Nations.

⁴⁴ National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement, “[MUPI Purposeful Partnerships cards](#)”, accessed November 13, 2024, <https://www.publicengagement.ac.uk/resources/tools-and-frameworks/mupi-purposeful-partnerships-cards>.

Think together about time and resources when planning your collaborative research project. How much time can each partner commit to the project? If you're starting with a small research project, to build your relationship, do you have the time to do the research yourselves? If so, then what roles and responsibilities will work best for each partner? This might depend on what strengths each wants to develop, or build on, and how involved each wants to be, given their context. It might be helpful to review the different levels of stakeholder engagement in [section 5](#) above, to see how much involvement partners may want. If your research will involve collecting data from people, it should go through the TU Dublin [ethical review process](#).

Some key ethical questions to consider:

- How can you make sure that everyone you collaborate with is cared for, and benefits from the research?
- How can you engage with a diversity of stakeholders, particularly with people whose voices are not often heard in research?
- How can you include everyone's perspectives when making decisions about the research, including the voices of children and/or vulnerable adults, where applicable?
- Can you agree and explain the goals of the research in simple, clear language, checking that you and different stakeholders understand key words in the same way?
- Can you agree and explain in simple language how you will protect the rights of people who share data with you? How will you fully anonymise their data, if they don't want to be identifiable?
- As the research develops, how will you check with stakeholders that you are representing their views accurately? Does the research still respond to their concerns, and is it intended to benefit society?
- How will you honestly communicate the results of your research, even if you and your stakeholders had hoped for different results?
- How do you and your stakeholders intend to use the research to create positive change?

If you're thinking about a bigger project, there are other questions to think through with your partner.

- Will you need funding to hire someone to help with the research?
- Which funding bodies might have goals that fit with yours, and what funding calls are coming soon?
- Which partner(s) will recruit and supervise any new staff, administer and manage the funding and necessary reporting, contribute time to the project (which should be costed and included in the budget), and work to make sure that research output(s) are used to make change happen?
- How will all partners receive payments for their contributions, fairly and efficiently?

You should also discuss the developing plans with your line manager or supervisor. You will find it easier to develop the research project if they are on board from the start. They can be a valuable ally

as you set up your collaborative project. You can also find useful guidance in TU Dublin's [Collaborative Research with External Partners Policy](#).

The pre-award team in [Research Support Services](#) can help you identify funding streams and cost a proposal. The [Innovation and Knowledge Transfer](#) team can advise you if you need any legal documentation, particularly if you feel that you might generate valuable intellectual property together. Drawing up legal documents can be challenging, and may affect your relationships with your partners. This can be easier to navigate if you put time into growing the relationships at the early stages (see [Section 7c](#)).

7e. Collaboration during research projects, underpinned by reflection for learning

Collaborative work involves three crucial parts. These are:

- the **task** (the research engagement project)
- the **process** (*how* you do the work)
- the **relationships** (*who* you work with, and the quality of interactions and support).

You will need to mind all three parts during collaborative projects.⁴⁵

Your first project meeting is really important. It gives the partners time together, and helps to build relationships and trust. Here you can make concrete plans, agree how you'll communicate, and set manageable deadlines together.

Clear communication is essential in partnership working. At a basic level, if you finish a task but your partners don't know you have, they might waste time duplicating your work. Regular updates and constructive meetings help build a trusting, supportive, 'no-blame' environment. If challenges arise within the team (e.g. people not being able to deliver work as planned) it's best to name and discuss these as early as possible.⁴⁶ It's important to address any concerns directly with the person involved, even though you might feel uncomfortable about having this conversation. Helpful guidelines for planning a difficult conversation are available.⁴⁷ Conflict is an inevitable part of teamwork. The research encouragingly shows that if it's handled well, it can actually make teams stronger.⁴⁸

Effective collaborative teams regularly reflect on progress, processes and relationships. Individual and team reflection can help you to understand your own reactions, thoughts and behaviours, and those of your collaborative partners. Many useful reflection resources are available.⁴⁹

Teamwork and collaboration depend on participants having relevant competencies, or abilities. When you reflect regularly on your work, you become more aware of your areas of strength, and of where you might want to learn and develop new abilities. There are three main domains of learning:⁵⁰

- Cognitive (related to **knowing**: knowledge you have about things and about how to do things, such as analysing information to draw conclusions)

⁴⁵ Maureen Sheehy, *Partners Companion to Training for Transformation*, (Partners Training for Transformation 2001).

⁴⁶ Bryan et al, [Common Cause Research: Building Research Collaborations](#).

⁴⁷ For example see this helpful 4-step conversation template: <https://nvc.guide/>.

⁴⁸ Herman Brouwer et al., *The MSP Guide: How to Design and Facilitate Multi-Stakeholder Partnerships*, (Centre for Development Innovation, Wageningen University 2015), <https://edepot.wur.nl/358948>.

⁴⁹ For example see The University of Edinburgh's [reflection toolkit](#).

⁵⁰ Leslie Owen Wilson, "Taxonomies of Learning", *The Second Principle* (blog), (2020), <https://thesecondprinciple.com/essential-teaching-skills/taxonomies-of-learning/>.

- Behavioural or psychomotor (related to **doing**: skills you have and actions you take, such as facilitating discussions in meetings)
- Affective (related to **being**: values and attitudes you hold, such as respect and equality, and related feelings)

If you'd like to further develop your competencies for collaboration, contact the [Research Engagement Lead](#) for information and further resources.

Groups and teams generally follow clear patterns of development.⁵¹ They start with the 'forming' stage of getting to know each other. They can move to 'storming', where differences of opinion can occur as people start working more closely. If this stage is managed well, and the group doesn't get stuck, they should move on to 'norming' - building agreement on processes and approaches. Finally, effective teams progress to 'performing', when smooth systems and relationships deliver strong outcomes.⁵² Whenever a team changes – if someone leaves or joins – the group will have to re-form, and may go through all the stages again. Partners who reflect regularly as a team can identify barriers to performing.

At the end of a project, it's important for partners to look back over the collaborative process together. This final reflection can really help to pull out relevant learning.

It can be useful to consider specific reflective questions at the end of a project, such as:

- Which of your goals were achieved?
- Were there any goals that you didn't achieve, or any emerging goals that weren't in your original plans?
- What processes worked well, and which less well?
- What would you change, if you could go back?
- What energised you, and what stressed you?
- What could you have done together to generate more energy and reduce stress?
- What did you learn – about tasks, processes, or relationships?
- Would you work together again, and if so, what research could build on the project you've just finished?

7f. Collaboratively creating impact (1): dialogue, education and public engagement.

Research engagement focuses on making change happen. This can be changes to practices, products, policies, or even people - their values, skills, or knowledge. You will develop research outputs that you and your stakeholders can use to enable change and create impact. You can find examples in figure 7. You might like to read the [TU Dublin Research Impact Framework](#) for more detailed guidance on planning for impact.

Your research may develop:	You could generate impact in a number of ways, for example:
New knowledge	You might be looking for ideas for how to apply your research. You might want to develop 2-way educational activities and dialogue about your

⁵¹ Ben Brearley, "The 5 Stages of Team Development and How to Navigate Them", *Thoughtful Leader* (podcast), Sep 26, 2023, <https://www.thoughtfulleader.com/podcast/233/>.

⁵² Brearley, "The 5 Stages of Team Development".

	research with a wider audience. This exchange of knowledge can help you to learn how your research could be relevant to others.
New processes	Your research engagement partners might try using your new processes in their own organisations. After they have been trialled you could evaluate their effectiveness. You might want to share your processes and evaluation with other organisations or networks. You may develop training or online educational resources, to help stakeholders to build their capacity to make positive changes.
New products	You might want to make the designs openly available so that other people can build on and improve them. You might want to contact relevant stakeholder organisations to let them know about this. Depending on your partners and/or funders, you may want to license the designs and look for a production partner (note this is more about innovation than research).
Evidence that supports a change in policy, or a continuation of existing policy.	You may want to produce a policy brief or policy paper, and engage with policymakers, to persuade them to consider your research recommendations when they're writing policies. (See section 7g below which focuses on engaging with policymakers.)

Fig. 9. Examples of research outputs and potential impact activities.

You can exchange ideas with stakeholders about your research by developing and running education and public engagement activities. You can use a wide range of engagement methods, such as workshops, focus groups, roundtables, dialogues, future scenarios, or arts-based approaches.⁵³ More examples are captured in figure 8. You can also collaboratively produce outputs with your partners, such as articles, blogs,⁵⁴ podcasts or videos.⁵⁵ See [section 10](#) below for more resources.

⁵³ Kelli Rose Pearson et al., *Arts-Based Methods for Transformative Engagement: A Toolkit* (SUSPLACE 2018), <https://research.wur.nl/en/publications/arts-based-methods-for-transformative-engagement-a-toolkit>.

⁵⁴ Eóin Young and Lisa Quinn, *An Essential Guide to Writing Policy Briefs* (International Centre for Policy Advocacy 2017), <https://icpolicyadvocacy.org/sites/default/files/2024-04/icpa-policy-briefs-essential-guide.pdf>.

⁵⁵ See for example databases of engagement methods at <http://actioncatalogue.eu/search> and <https://involve.org.uk/resources/methods>.

Source: Maura Adshead graphic, 2020

Fig. 10. Illustration of a range of engaged research methods (Maura Adshead 2020)⁵⁶

Ask yourself these key questions⁵⁷ when designing an education or public engagement activity:

- Who are the people involved, both participants and facilitators?
- Why is there a need for this activity in this situation?
- What will be different as a result of this joint learning?
- When will the activity happen, and, crucially, how much time will be involved? This will determine how much learning can take place.
- Where will it happen? Why is this the best location, and are there any challenges in using this location?
- What will the content be – the knowledge, skills and/or values and attitudes that you'd like participants to focus on learning? What do you want to learn from them?
- How will participants learn these things – what will they actually do during the activity? How will you learn from them?

Adapted from Jane Vella and Global Learning Partners⁵⁸

⁵⁶ Maura Adshead, in Campus Engage, "Methodological Approaches for Engaging Diverse Stakeholders" (PowerPoint slides), Irish Universities Association.

⁵⁷ Vella, J., in Global Learning Practices, "The 8 Steps of Design – A Learning Framework", accessed November 13, 2024, https://www.globallearningpartners.com/wp-content/uploads/migrated/resources/8_Steps_of_Design.pdf

⁵⁸ Global Learning Partners, "The Eight Steps of Design – A Learning Design Framework", accessed November 13, 2024, https://www.globallearningpartners.com/wp-content/uploads/migrated/resources/8_Steps_of_Design.pdf.

It's also worth building some quiet or reflective space into your educational activities, to help people to process their learning.⁵⁹

If you will be collecting data from people as part of these activities, you will need to go through the TU Dublin ethical review process first. You can find useful materials online to help with developing information and consent forms.⁶⁰

If you're interested in dialogue and engagement with the local community, the TU Dublin Access and Outreach team run activities with schools and community organisations. There could be opportunities for you to develop and run a workshop/initiative as part of their programmes. Contact TU Dublin's [Research Impact Lead](#) if you'd like to link in with the Access and Outreach team.

If you're interested in training on public relations and communications, to help you raise awareness of the impact of your research, contact TU Dublin's [R+ Marketing and Communications team](#).

7g. Collaboratively creating impact (2): engaging with policymakers.

As mentioned above, your research may generate evidence that a change of policy is needed, or even a continuation of existing policy. You can make the case for this by engaging with policymakers. This can help to increase the impact of your research.

Policies are made at a range of different levels:

- Organisational level (eg in the university or in a community organisation)
- Local or community level (across local networks or sectors)
- Regional level (e.g. local government)
- National level (e.g. government departments, or national bodies)
- International level (e.g. the European Commission, or international bodies such as the UN)

It can be easier to influence policy at a local level, but you can potentially have more impact at a national or international level. There are different ways to engage with stakeholders to influence policy.

You can look for relevant calls for policy submissions (for example current national policy consultations are listed [here](#)). Most policy consultations involve a survey or request for written submissions. Some may also involve focus groups, and/or a follow-up stage, such as a workshop, to which the policymakers may invite people who made a written submission. These can be positive opportunities to influence the direction of policy. Live events can be a great way to meet policymakers, and others interested in your area of research or practice.

You might like to write a policy brief, which is a short non-technical summary of your research recommendations for policymakers, supported by relevant evidence.⁶¹ There are specific resources available on writing policy briefs, which tend to follow a particular format (see [section 10](#) below for more details on these). You will want to bring this brief to the attention of relevant policymakers.

⁵⁹ Jane Vella, "The Praxis of Dialogue". Global Learning Partners (blog), April 13, 2015, <https://www.globallearningpartners.com/blog/the-praxis-of-dialogue/>.

⁶⁰ See for example UCD Human Research Ethics Committee's [Guideline: Informed Consent in Research](#) and [Guideline: Information Sheet/Consent Form Examples](#).

⁶¹ Young and Quinn, [An Essential Guide to Writing Policy Briefs](#).

Policymakers are more likely to read your brief if you (or your research partners) have some connection to them. Look for committees that you could join, where decisions or policies are developed. This can help you to build a reputation as an advocate for positive social change, based on reliable research evidence. You can then build relationships with relevant policymakers – see more detail on building relationships in [section 7c](#) above. You might ask key policymakers to meet you to discuss your research (e.g. local government officials, senior civil servants, government ministers). You may want to hold a workshop or event on the policy implications of your research, and invite policymakers and other stakeholder groups.

It will be easier to engage with relevant policymakers if your research was done in collaboration with stakeholders. Your partnership will have wider networks and connections than an individual researcher would. It's important to share credit with your stakeholder partners when you are working with policymakers. It's also important that all partners have equal opportunities to meet with policymakers. This demonstrates values of inclusion and respect, and helps balance the power dynamics in research partnerships (see [section 7c](#) for more details).

You might like to read the [TU Dublin Research Impact Framework](#). This contains more detailed guidance on how to plan for research impact, measure it, and communicate and report it effectively.

If you're interested in training on public relations and communications, to help you raise awareness of the impact of your research, contact TU Dublin's [R+I Marketing and Communications](#).

7h. Wrapping up or building on engaged research relationships and project(s)

As a collaborative research project comes to an end, it's important to reflect with partners on the tasks, processes and relationships (see [section 7e](#) above).

The partners may decide to build on the collaboration and start a new project. It's important to once again map all the stakeholders (see [section 7a](#) above), and engage respectfully with them (section 7b) to collaboratively develop a new research question and proposal. You can learn from your final reflection on the previous project. For example, you may agree to change some behaviours or processes, to build on your strengths and avoid repeating earlier mistakes.

The partners may agree that the collaboration has run its course, and their key goals have been achieved. Or they may not have the time, resources or interest to collaborate again. Either way it's important to celebrate what has been achieved. When the tasks and processes are complete, it's important to honour the relationships that made it all possible. You could organise coffee and a cake, a meal together, a final reflection, an exhibition or publication, to positively mark the end of the collaboration. Your paths may cross later in unexpected ways, so make sure to finish the project well. If you find you want to get back in touch later, it's easier after a positive ending.

8. Essential supports and structures: processes, roles and relevant contacts

TU Dublin offers a range of supports for research engagement.

The [Research Engagement and Impact Office](#) can support you with research partnership processes. We can help you to identify stakeholders and external partners who might be interested in your research. We can also support you to plan, monitor and communicate the impact of your research engagement. You might like to join the university's [Engaged Research Network](#), to meet colleagues

who are also interested in research engagement. [Contact](#) the TU Dublin Research Engagement Lead or Research Impact Lead if you'd like to have a chat.

If you're organising research engagement events, the [Research Engagement and Impact Office](#) can support you, for example with marketing and communications, booking locations, and useful forms that will be required as part of your event preparation. You can fill out the [event planning form](#), or [contact the team](#), if you have an event in mind.

The [Head of Research Ethics and Integrity](#) can offer guidance on the [ethical review process](#).

The [Pre-award team](#) in Research Support Services can help you find funding opportunities to support your plans for research engagement or engaged research projects.

The [ARISE Business Developers](#) can help link you in with industry stakeholders.

The [Societal Engagement team](#) can help you to engage in the Living Lab pilots they are running, if you'd like to explore sustainability on the campus with stakeholders.

The [TU Dublin Innovation team](#) can support you if your research engagement is likely to generate outputs that can be commercialised or patented.

9. General resources, checklists and forms

Campus Engage has produced very useful resources for universities on doing research engagement. You can find their recently updated 'how-to guides' and case studies [here](#). Their [Engaged Research Framework](#) contains a helpful checklist for planning research engagement.

The Wheel has produced a [research proposal form](#), which can help you to clarify why you want to partner with a community organisation. They have also produced a sample [memorandum of understanding](#) (or agreement to collaborate). Their [research planning template](#) for community partners can help you to understand their perspectives on research collaboration.

Next Generation's [Guide for Research Partnership Agreements](#) includes checklists for planning engaged research projects. It can also be used to develop a detailed Memorandum of Understanding.

Global Learning Partners produced a [planning checklist](#), which can guide you through the steps of designing an education and public engagement activity.

The Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth have a very useful [planning checklist](#) for engaging with children. You could adapt the checklist for collaboration with other vulnerable stakeholders.

UCD have produced useful [guidance](#) and [templates](#) for information and consent forms for participants in engagement activities. You will need to develop these if you will be collecting data from them.

In TU Dublin, research engagement activities are covered by relevant policies and procedures:

- If you are planning to collect data from participants as part of your research engagement, you can find the TU Dublin Research Ethics and Integrity processes and application forms [here](#).
- If you are working with children or vulnerable adults, you can find helpful guidance in the TU Dublin Policy [Safeguarding and Protection of Children, Young Persons and Vulnerable Adults](#)
- If you are going to bring stakeholders onto campus and organise research engagement events, you can find a checklist on what you need to do [here](#).

You might like to read the [TU Dublin Research Impact Framework](#) for more detailed guidance on how to plan for research impact, measure it, and communicate it effectively.

10. Further exploration: resources linked to each of element of the framework

These 4 detailed resources explore research engagement generally:

- You can find helpful process guides and detailed practice tips on all aspects of research engagement in [Brouwer, Herman and Jim Woodhill with Minu Hemmati, Karèn Verhoosel and Simone van Vugt. *The MSP guide: how to design and facilitate multi-stakeholders partnerships*. Wageningen: CDI, 2015.](#)
- All stages of the research collaboration process are covered in this guide (which focuses on researcher-artist collaborations with the public, but is applicable to all collaborations): [NCCPE. *What Works: Artist and Researcher Collaborations. A guide from the NCCPE and network contributors*. Bristol: NCCPE, 2021.](#)
- This is an excellent guide to ethics in engaged research: [Centre for Social Justice and Community Action & National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement. *Community-based participatory research: A guide to ethical principles and practice*. 2nd edition. Durham and Bristol: CSJCA & NCCPE, 2022.](#)
- This EU report highlights ways to engage with the public to test the effectiveness of research: [European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. *Fostering knowledge valorisation through citizen engagement*. 2024. DOI: 10.2777/007501](#)

These resources explore elements of the Research Engagement Framework in more detail:

(a) On **identifying, mapping and prioritising stakeholders**:

- Part 3 of this guide (page 34 on) contains detailed guidance on identifying, prioritizing and understanding stakeholders: [Durham, Emma, Helen Baker, Matt Smith, Elizabeth Moore and Vicky Morgan. *The BiodivERsA Stakeholder Engagement Handbook*. Paris: BiodivERsA, 2014.](#)
- This series of 10 blogposts explores how to work with research stakeholders. Blogposts 1-3 explore defining, identifying and selecting stakeholders: [Bammer, Gabrielle. “Stakeholder engagement primer: 1a. Why a primer? 1b. Defining stakeholders”, *Integration and Implementation Insights \(blog\)*, October 14th, 2021. <https://i2insights.org/2021/10/14/defining-stakeholders/>.](#)
- This resource offers guidance on how you might engage with disabled people in your research. This is not just relevant for Public and Patient Involvement (or PPI) on medical or

disability-related research, but for all research topics. For example, pages 35-39 consider who you might involve, and how to find them: National Disability Authority, *Collaborative research with disabled people: Guidance for researchers* (October 2023),

https://nda.ie/uploads/publications/Co-research-Guidance-Final-Guidance_2023.docx

- Pages 21-27 of this research engagement toolkit for PPI consider how to identify and potentially contact stakeholders: Lambert, Veronica, Linda Dillon, Iryna Pokhilo, Collette Tully, Michelle Gardner, Derick Mitchell, Orla Collins, Mary Clare O'Hara, *Framework for Public Involvement in Clinical Effectiveness Processes* (Dublin: Department of Health, 2018), <https://www.gov.ie/pdf/?file=https://assets.gov.ie/10799/6bed89196b67497ebc22a1b9dc3e1f8b.pdf>,

(b) On **making contact with stakeholders**:

- This article is about building relationships with co-workers, but many of the same points apply to stakeholders. [Ng, Gorick. "How to Build Real Relationships at Work", *Harvard Business Review*, August 19 \(2022\), https://hbr.org/2022/08/how-to-build-real-relationships-at-work.](https://hbr.org/2022/08/how-to-build-real-relationships-at-work)
- This article is about developing a stakeholder engagement plan. Steps 6 onwards focus on planning, doing and learning from actual engagement with stakeholders. [Hollmann, Susanne, Babette Regierer, Jaele Bechis, Lesley Tobin, and Domenica D'Elia. "Ten simple rules on how to develop a stakeholder engagement plan". *PLoS Computational Biology*. 18 no. 10, \(October 2022\). doi: 10.1371/journal.pcbi.1010520](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1010520)

(c) On **building relationships for mutual benefit** - with stakeholders/ partners/ interdisciplinary teams:

- This manual offers guidance on all stages of planning research collaborations. It focuses on particular societal groups but can be applied to anyone. [David Bryan, Katherine Dunleavy, Keri Facer, Charles Forsdick, Omar Khan, Mhemooda Malek, Karen Salt, and Kristy Warren. *Common Cause Research: Building Research Collaborations Between Universities and Black and Minority Ethnic Communities*. Bristol: University of Bristol and the Arts and Humanities Research Council Connected Communities Programme 2018.](https://www.bristol.ac.uk/arts-and-humanities-research-council/research-collaborations-between-universities-and-black-and-minority-ethnic-communities/)
- This pack provides helpful reflection prompts which you can use yourself or with partners [Aurbach, E.L., E. Kuhn, H. Sdvizhkov, and R.K. Niemer. "Public Engagement Framework Reflection Decks - Relationships Workbook". *The Michigan Public Engagement Reflection Decks, Version 3.0*. Michigan: University of Michigan, 2021.](https://www.umich.edu/public-engagement-reflection-decks/)
- This guide offers valuable insights into researchers' and charities' perspective on research collaboration. See pages 15-16 in particular for recommendations for researchers. HRCI and the PPI Ignite Network, *Charities & Researchers Partnering for Societal Benefit* (Dublin and Galway: HRCI and PPI Ignite, 2023) <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1G7Yf9tBLhGHgmrU8AWBOPlgjOITNyZ/view>
- This is a guide to research collaboration, for and by early career researchers. Pages 6-7 outline success factors for research collaborations, and practical tips to achieve them. [LERU Doctoral Summer School. *Research Collaborations: A Guide for Early Career Researchers by Early Career Researchers*. The University of Edinburgh. Accessed November 14, 2024.](https://www.ed.ac.uk/early-career-researchers/)
- This resource for engaging with children as stakeholders can also be adapted for working with other vulnerable groups. [Department of Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and](https://www.doh.gov.ie/en/children-and-family/department-of-children-equality-disability-integration-and)

[Youth. Participation Framework: National Framework for Children and Young People's Participation in Decision-making. Accessed November 14, 2024.](#) It contains a useful framework and practical tips - see page 18 for a helpful planning checklist. It also contains case studies, see for example page 35-8 on facilitating the development of a youth-led action plan.

(d) On **collaboratively designing research projects**, and clarifying ethics, roles and responsibilities.

- This article considers 7 different levels of community engagement in research. It gives both researcher and community perspectives on each. [Key, Kent D., Debra Furr-Holden, E. Yvonne Lewis, Rebecca Cunningham, Marc A. Zimmerman, Vicki Johnson-Lawrence, Suzanne Selig. "The Continuum of Community Engagement in Research: A Roadmap for Understanding and Assessing Progress". *Progress in Community Health Partnerships Research Education and Action*, 13 no. 4. \(Winter 2019\): 427-434. DOI: 10.1353/cpr.2019.0064](#)
- This engaged research framework helpfully breaks down the different stages of research projects, and suggests different options for collaboration for each stage. [Campus Engage. *Engaged Research Framework 2022.*](#)
- This article explores the evidence about making research collaborations successful. They focus on academic partnerships but the principles relate to all kinds of collaborations. [Ravasi, Davide, Jing Zhu, William Wan, Sinziana Dorobantu, and Marc Gruber. "What Makes Research Collaborations Successful? Advice from AMJ Authors". *Academy of Management Journal*, 67 No. 3 \(Jun 27, 2024\). <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2024.4003>.](#)
- This is a very useful guide for thinking through the ethics of research collaboration: [Centre for Social Justice and Community Action & National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement. *Community-based participatory research: A guide to ethical principles and practice. 2nd edition.* Durham and Bristol: CSJCA & NCCPE, 2022.](#)

(e) On **collaboration during research projects**, underpinned by reflection and evaluation:

- You can find helpful process guides and practice tips on collaboration with partners, including communication, negotiation, reflection and conflict, in [Brouwer, Herman and Jim Woodhill with Minu Hemmati, Karèn Verhoosel and Simone van Vugt. *The MSP guide: how to design and facilitate multi-stakeholders partnerships.* Wageningen: CDI, 2015.](#)
- You can find detailed instructions for creative reflection exercises here: [Gordijn, Femke, with Natalia Eernstman, Jan Helder and Herman Brouwer. *Reflection methods. Practical guide for trainers and facilitators.* Wageningen: CDI, Wageningen University and Research, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.18174/439461>.](#)
- This short guide gives evidence for the value of reflection, and simple tools for doing reflection. [Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development, with Grace Owen and Alison Fletcher. "Reflective Practice Guide". Accessed November 14, 2024.](#)
- You can learn more about facilitating effective teams, and the roles that people can choose to take in groups, in [Isaacs, William N. "Dialogic Leadership". *The Systems Thinker.* 2018.](#)

(f) On **collaboratively creating impact (1): dialogue, education and public engagement.**

- You can find clear, detailed instructions for a range of arts-based exercises in this guide. These could work well in stakeholder engagement sessions. Kelli Rose Pearson, Malin

Bäckman, Sara Grenni, Angela Moriggi, Siri Pisters, and Anke de Vrieze. *Arts-Based Methods for Transformative Engagement: A Toolkit*. (SUSPLACE 2018)
<https://doi.org/10.18174/441523>.

- You can find a useful short checklist for planning educational activities here: [Vella, J., in Global Learning Practices, “The 8 Steps of Design – A Learning Framework”, accessed November 13, 2024.](#)
- You can find 2 searchable databases of methods to engage with stakeholders here: <http://actioncatalogue.eu> and <https://involve.org.uk/resources/methods>
- You might like to read the [TU Dublin Research Impact Framework](#) for more detailed guidance on how to plan for research impact, measure it, and communicate it effectively.

(g) On **collaboratively creating impact (2): engaging with policymakers.**

- You can find guidance on writing policy papers here:
 - [Young, Éoin and Lisa Quinn. *An Essential Guide to Writing Policy Briefs*. Berlin: International Centre for Policy Advocacy, 2017.](#)
 - [Young, Éoin and Lisa Quinn. *Writing Effective Public Policy Papers - A Guide for Policy Advisers in Central and Eastern Europe*. Budapest: Local Government and Public Service Reform Initiative, Open Society Institute, 2002.](#) (This document is more detailed than the authors’ 2017 publication, and contains useful background information about policy-making contexts and processes.)
 - [Pennock, Andrew. *The CQ Press Writing Guide for Public Policy*. California: SAGE Publications, 2019.](#)
- This is a short, simple, clear introduction to influencing policy. It focuses on influencing policy to embed community engaged research into higher education, but the principles apply across policy areas. [McKenna, Emma and Eileen Martin. *A Practical Guide to Developing Policy and Strategy*. Belfast: Queen's University Belfast Science Shop, 2013.](#)
- This detailed guide supports researchers to influence policy in three key stages. These are: mapping and analysing the issue and its causes, developing a strategy to influence policymakers, and monitoring progress against your goals to maximise your learning. [Young, John, Louise Shaxson, Harry Jones, Simon Hearn, Ajoy Datta, and Caroline Cassidy. *RAPID Outcome Mapping Approach - a guide to policy engagement and influence*. London: Overseas Development Institute, 2014.](#)
- You might like to read the [TU Dublin Research Impact Framework](#) for more detailed guidance on how to plan for research impact, measure it, and communicate it effectively.

(h) On **wrapping up or building on engaged research relationships and projects:**

- See the ‘legacy’ section and onwards in this guide. The guide is on researcher-artist collaborations with the public, but the ideas are relevant across disciplines. [NCCPE. *What Works: Artist and Researcher Collaborations. A guide from the NCCPE and network contributors*. Bristol: NCCPE, 2021.](#)

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